

Lisbon working for circular economy in FORCE project

Lisbon Municipality participated in FORCE project from September 1st, 2016 to February 28th, 2021 (<http://www.ce-force.eu/>).

The FORCE project aimed to develop circular economy circuits in four waste categories: food waste, plastic, wood and Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment.

The consortium consisted of four main partners, each responsible for developing one circuit for circular economy for one of the waste streams, along with a group of national partners. Each of the main partners was responsible for replicating the business plan created by the other partners in the waste streams the others were responsible for.

Lisbon Municipality was responsible for the Work package on food waste, counting with the partnership of Dar e Acordar, Addapters, AHRESP, Valorsul e Quercus.

Considering the other waste streams, it was not possible for Lisbon to follow the business plan created by the other partners, and the municipality implemented other initiatives to develop circular economy in those waste streams.

Here we will present the results in the four waste streams, with special focus on food waste recovery.

Food waste recovery

A digital platform was developed, based on the ZERO DESPERDÍCIO operational model, already implemented in more than 21 cities and municipalities in Portugal, by DARIACORDAR. The aim was to build a new digital tool to optimize the process of managing and redistributing food surpluses and reducing food waste in the overall production, distribution, and consumption cycle.

The ZERO WASTE operational model mainly focused on preventing the surplus and recovering where it occurs, promoting new perspectives and impacts in the economy, politics, legal and society through behavioural transformation and definition of political-administrative, environmental, social, ethical and economic best practices.

A WEBAPP was created (<https://www.lisboazero.app/>) for the partners to easily introduce their data and their interest in donating or receiving food, in order to facilitate the process between both parts.

In the platform it is possible to access the information on:

- The municipal waste recovery in different circuits (<https://www.lisboazero.app/en/lisboa-in-action-in-numbers/>)

On the website are also presented the following data for the 1,5 final year of the project, for the five circuits presented in the chart above:

- Amount collected in weight
- Installed containers
- Average number of monthly collections
- Average of collected waste, in weight, by entity

- The main results in reducing food waste (<https://www.lisboazero.app/en/impacts-in-lisbon/>):

The donated food was received by institutions of social solidarity, families, children, old-aged people and homeless people, distributed over a major part of the city:

The donor entities have a big expression all over the city:

Considering the parishes, de donors and receivers is the following:

(Green dots – receivers; Pink dots – donors)

The donated food was registered according several categories, namely: Drinks, Cooked food, Fruits and vegetables, Dairy products, Grocery, Bakery and pastry, Chilled and frozen food products and Soup.

The biggest amount of donated food was cooked food, representing more than half of the donations. Associated with Fruits and vegetables (14%) and Grocery (11%) these 3 categories represent more than 75% of the donated food.

Distributed by month, the donation of food was as follow:

	Drinks	Cooked food	Fruits and vegetables	Dairy products	Grocery	Bakery and pastry	Chilled and frozen food products	Soup
Oct 2018		15 943,78			11 396,00		202,00	3 622,00
Nov 2018		14 909,78			10 462,00		422,00	4 418,00
Dec 2018		16 767,78			5 430,00		268,00	2 134,00
Jan 2019	1 191,30	31 355,60	150,40	27,19	5 257,26	572,60	3 472,93	389,20
Feb 2019	568,00	28 588,60	390,00	78,80	4 861,20	456,04	3 740,00	409,20
March 2019	796,00	28 228,80	19,80	34,00	4 202,00	302,63	2 478,00	311,20
April 2019	432,00	23 926,70	38,00	10,00	4 174,31	695,34	2 903,50	334,40
May 2019	902,00	28 800,40	456,00	42,75	4 424,00	546,80	4 730,00	541,20
June 2019	942,00	17 806,40	495,60	51,00	1 885,00	507,36	2 022,00	290,00
July 2019	444,00	19 257,66	126,00	49,25	7 948,85	331,23	1 858,96	346,00
Aug 2019	268,00	22 952,40			5 288,00		1 680,00	
Sept 2019	766,60	26 736,75	68,00	15,00	4 228,22	658,36	2 734,04	338,00
Oct 2019	635,79	31 947,73	52,00	46,40	6 211,53	530,70	3 486,74	383,60
Nov 2019	294,70	22 180,02	38,00		7 781,58	588,92	4 155,14	389,20
Dec 2019	166,10	28 072,64	22,00	4,00	7 210,91	617,91	4 333,07	147,60
Jan 2020	554,82	97 556,59	312,60	948,71	1 580,31	6 782,50	5 240,32	127,00
Feb 2020	1 033,76	95 979,51	163,00	794,60	2 099,14	10 016,81	7 443,21	1 355,20
March 2020	150,36	84 815,71	606,00	750,77	299,45	4 143,27	678,88	1 234,00
April 2020		2 487,06	886,00	410,30	25,30	3 165,37	44,84	248,00
May 2020	373,10	4 992,06	4 476,00	304,23	276,85	3 527,12	1 228,38	367,60
June 2020	518,22	8 459,75	5 426,00	587,77	346,80	9 128,30	1 748,25	833,60
July 2020	573,78	14 786,74	5 488,00	810,11	536,32	10 685,33	2 570,37	1 215,20
Aug 2020	675,16	87 313,18	4 416,00	80 814,18	470,26	8 294,53	2 530,88	704,00
Sept 2020	828,36	93 672,12	8 065,38	763,40	83 012,01	9 982,23	61,40	821,20
Oct 2020	532,50	89 049,45	7 472,66	682,79	1 273,77	10 002,49	97,53	682,60
Nov 2020	433,38	6 165,06	85 648,00	1 142,39	1 329,40	12 744,37	5 718,32	614,00
Dec 2020	227,24	4 735,37	85 554,50	947,85	1 183,67	8 246,47	4 164,44	378,00
Jan 2021	199,08	5 968,16	21 925,55	1 178,41	2 405,41	6 288,21	5 197,00	645,00
Feb 2021	218,16	6 859,45	12 778,26	1 846,32	2 699,22	8 169,18	5 007,24	297,00
Total (equivalent meals)	13 724,41	960 315,25	245 073,75	92 340,22	188 298,77	116 984,07	80 217,44	23 576,00

Chart - Amount of food recovered in equivalent meals per month

Also, with the FORCE project Lisbon started the development of a project for the families to be able to send their waste food for composting: Lisboa a compostar (<https://lisboaacompostar.cm-lisboa.pt/>). In this project the families receive a composter to do their composting at home or are given access to a community composter in public gardens. The families also receive a training session on how to do their composting.

As can be seen in the image below, the population is joining the initiative with a lot of interest, with the following numbers at this point:

- 6 515 registries in the platform Lisboa a compostar
- 4 412 participants in the awareness sessions
- 145 training sessions in person + 85 online training sessions
- 3 088 composters delivered face to face
- 19 community composters in the city
- 817 participants in community composting
- 9,01 in level of satisfaction (from 1 to 10)
- 772 tonnes of recovered waste per year

Plastic waste recovery

In this WP Lisbon Municipality made a partnership with Valorsul, responsible for the treatment and recovery of municipal waste, and Mistaker Maker Association, a Platform for Artistic Intervention.

The goal here was to use recovered plastic as a source of raw material for art pieces. However, analysing the collected plastic it was concluded that this waste stream would be unviable, as a source of secondary raw materials for upcycling, with art purposes, despite the pre-preparing effort (prewashing and storage). Alternatively, another waste stream was available, a depot of discarded waste containers, that were discarded by the city, either due to failure in service or obsolescence. This solution made it not possible to measure the amount of plastic that was used to make art pieces and the CO₂ emissions avoided. However, the way that the plastic was used in art pieces had a big impact in the population, not only in Lisbon but at the national level, being animals the resulting pieces.

The artistic work resulted in:

- 41 art pieces shown to over 27 000 visitors in the Attero exhibition, by the artist Bordalo II, many of them created using secondary raw materials sourced through the FORCE project;
- Several pieces of art, also made by the artist Bordalo II, were placed in a few locations of the city, to get the artwork closer to the public. Through the official artists' Facebook and Instagram page, it is possible to see that the images of 4 of the public artworks produced received over 62 900 likes.

Also, a video raising awareness to plastic use was made by the municipality in the COVID timeframe (<https://vimeo.com/637586435>).

Globally, the Attero exhibition reached 27 000 persons with 41 artworks, eight posts in 2 social networks regarding four public art pieces reached 62 900 persons and one video on the municipality's website got over 4 800 views.

WEEE recovery

The Lisbon Municipality has created two recurring repair cafés in the centre of the city to decrease the amount of discarded Waste of Electric and Electronic Equipment (WEEE).

The repair cafés were implemented in municipal facilities and a municipal market in a popup model in a partnership between:

- FabLab Lisboa – Responsible for event planning and organization, installations and equipment, logistics, professional technicians to support the self-repair initiatives.
- Municipal Directorate of Urban Hygiene (DMHU) – Responsible for installations and equipment, logistic support, professional technicians to support the self-repair initiatives.
- Circular Economy Portugal – Responsible for event planning and organization support.
- Citizen volunteers' group – Volunteer citizens to support the self-repair initiatives.

The Repair Cafés have been developed in 3 principal venues:

- At the FabLab workshop. A fully staffed and equipped installation located in the Forno do Tijolo Municipal market, located in Arroios Parish Council.
- At DMHU fleet garage, located in Olivais Parish Council. A workshop with specialized services not available in other municipal locations and suitable to develop face-to-face awareness actions towards bringing citizens closer to the city's waste management process.
- A pilot on-line event or organized during the COVID19 pandemic.

From November 2016 to August 2020, 24 repair cafés were performed at the FabLab workshop.

An estimated 1,123 kg of WEEE was avoided through the organization of 27 Popup Repair Cafés.

In January 2021 it was possible to organize a pilot on-line Repair Café in order to adapt to the COVID19 pandemic.

Wood recovery

The concept of reoccurring pop-up Repair Cafés was developed by FabLab Lisboa, a municipal digital fabrication and prototyping laboratory, aimed at supporting creativity and developing new collaborative projects, through access to knowledge and equipment. FabLab is incorporated in the Municipal Directorate of Economy and Innovation. These repair cafés were firstly designed for WEEE recovery, but due to constrains in having specific installations for wood recovery, the repair cafés were also directed for the recovery of wood furniture.

The organisation of the Repair Cafés has been based on an informal partnership between four entities, namely:

- FabLab Lisboa – Responsible for event planning and organisation, installations and equipment, logistics, professional technicians to support the self-repair initiatives.
- Municipal Directorate of Urban Hygiene (DMHU) – Responsible for installations and equipment, logistic support, professional technicians to support the self-repair initiatives.
- Circular Economy Portugal – Responsible for event planning and organisation support.
- Citizen volunteers' group – Volunteer citizens to support the self-repair initiatives.

Having to “leave behind” a first place in Beato Hub, that was only starting the process of recovering the space, the Lisbon Municipality found another spot and created “Ripas”, a reuse centre open to all residents of Lisbon who wish to participate in activities to reuse and repair used wood items and furniture. To ensure the supply of items of adequate quality to the Ripas centre, additional sorting has been implemented at the City's reception centres of bulky waste. Thus, the reception centres equipped to receive wood waste for recycling were expanded from two to four, increasing the amount of wood recycled yearly by 1,368 tonnes. Although the Ripas space was ready in the timeframe of the project, COVID constrains only allowed its opening

The results of the activities initiated and conducted:

- 374 kg (estimated) of wood waste avoided through the organisation of 27 pop-up Repair Cafés.
- Additionally, 2,84 tonnes of furniture were recovered in the fleet garage for reuse in municipal facilities.
- By implementing wood waste containers in two additional municipal reception centres, it was possible to increase the amount of wood collected by 1 368 tonnes yearly.
- Redesigning the green waste (including brushwood) collection routes made it possible to divert this waste stream from incineration to composting.
- A new reuse centre for wood selected from the bulky waste collection service was established.